

FEATURES OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING TO STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS BASED ON BLENDED LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *In today's transformational processes, it is necessary to consider the traditional views on education from a new perspective and acquire new approach skills based on the needs of the times. This means, consistently in place, the active implementation of innovations, the integration of science and production into the educational process. Education is our future, therefore, it is necessary to reconsider the approach to the education system and introduce new teaching standards into the traditional teaching model.*

Keywords: *blended learning, methods, techniques, approaches, course, students.*

Introduction: Currently, most of the research projects in the field of education of various international organizations are dedicated to the in-depth knowledge and effectiveness of the 21st century, which is necessary for the formation of the knowledge economy. These studies are the criteria and benchmarks of educational standards; aimed at determining the impact of information and communication technologies or we can say information communicative technologies on the educational system in the context of the level of international requirements[1].

In 2011, UNESCO and the International Society for Information Technologies in Education presented an updated version of the document (the first edition was published in 2008) developed in cooperation with leading experts in the field of school information technology. It defines the standards of teacher competence in the application of ICT-UNESCO's ICT Competency Framework for Teachers (here in after referred to as the recommendations of UNESCO ICT-CFT). According to the analyzes presented in the documents, the existence of norms and certain criteria is not enough to implement complete changes in the educational process[2]. It is necessary to involve pedagogues in the active use of innovative technologies in the educational process. UNESCO's conceptual framework for competency standards in the field of teachers' use of ICT is created at the intersection of three different approaches to education reform, that is, based on the development of human abilities: technical literacy; deepening and building of knowledge; the six components of the education system are policies, programs, pedagogy, ICT, teacher integration and training competencies[3].

Research methodology: Currently, the development of information and communication technologies leads to the emergence of new types of pedagogical innovations. A special NMS HORIZON consortium was established (<https://www.nmc.org/publication>) on innovations currently used in foreign higher education institutions, "NMS HORIZON report: higher education - 2020" discusses important technological developments that will have a high impact on the world education system in the near future. In the report, an analysis was conducted in the context of the main trends and problems that may affect the educational process in the future. The group of experts will revise the content of higher education on the basis of ideas about how higher education will be in the future, its ultimate goals or objectives and for whom it is intended, adapting to trends

and changes in people's thinking, as well as social, political and economic relations. who touched on the need for review. Also, future models of higher education, teaching practices, delivery of non-traditional courses, readiness of teachers to teach online, acquisition of competences for working in blended learning mode, development of digital skills are several. who mentioned their priority tasks. This, in turn, refers to the main trends in the improvement of the innovative culture, the need to create reworked curricula that encourage the promotion of the culture of innovation in the field of education, the development of modern teaching strategies and the educational system helps globalization[4].

In our opinion, it is emphasized that a new approach to education is important and effective in the process of modernization of the field of education during the next decade. However, in any field, it is important to always take into account the uniqueness of the local mentality and culture when making changes to the educational process in this case.

It is known that in Europe and the United States of America, the problems and difficulties arising from the organization of the educational process based on mixed education, the implementation of mixed education models, as well as the prospects for the development of mixed education in higher education are discussed[5]. 8-10 years ago, it was widely analyzed in academic and business circles and interpreted as a new educational model that is gaining popularity.

The experience of foreign countries shows that the popularity of mixed education in the United States of America, Europe and Russia is not only an opportunity to increase the effectiveness of the educational process through an optimal combination of the advantages offered by traditional education and distance learning technologies, but also due to economic reasons, costs associated with the choice of "economical" methods of information delivery to solve assigned tasks, for example, facilities such as placing educational materials on the network, using educational content management systems.

It is known that the concept of Blended learning is understood as a teaching model based on the combination of distance and traditional education[6].

Blended learning is defined by the Clayton Christensen Institute as follows: blended learning is a modern educational technology that combines brick and mortar education with online learning. (e-Learning) combines with receiving and assumes independent control of the speed, location, time of the learning process by the learner, as well as the integration of the experience of learning together with the teacher and online.

Blended education combines traditional and distance learning technologies. This educational technology does not require abandoning traditional (Brick and Mortar Education) education, because traditional education (reading in the auditorium) helps to develop speech and socio-cultural skills that are important for the individual. will help. In English, it is called Brick and Mortar (brick and mortar) which means traditional, "used for a long time". Brick and Mortar Education refers to the traditional model of comprehensive education. In this, the learner participates in classes held in auditoriums, but at the same time uses Computer-Mediated Activities tools. That is, a computer, online mode, mobile devices and special educational programs/platforms/resources act as mediators of educational activity.

Blended learning technology can be applied to different audiences. In particular, the use of students in education, training, professional development.

The term "blended learning technology" was first introduced in 1999 in a press release by the Interactive Learning Center of the United States of America and was proposed by them to be

called "EPIC Learning". In the media materials it is said: "...We use our Blended Learning methodology and provide software for online education".

Oliver and Trigwell (2005) noted that the increased interest in the problem of blended learning is explained by the active use of information technology in the educational process, while Bonk and Graham (2006) described blended learning as face-to-face instruction and computer-aided computer-mediated instruction are defined as a combination of education.

Today, blended learning refers to the combination of Internet and classroom digital media learning opportunities[7].

According to the analysis, the US organization Innosight Institute (www.innosightinstitute.org) has been studying the experiences of implementing mixed education in American schools since 2007. In the annual reports of this organization, the results of school students are given, and it is noted that they are always much higher than the results of students who are taught in traditional education. In our opinion, this situation can be attributed to the fact that mixed education is based on the integration of various forms of work (lectures in the auditorium, remote independent work, online consultations, tutoring services, etc.).

Also, it is no exaggeration to call modern education a type of mixed education to some extent, because digital technologies are the main source of knowledge and experience. But despite this, according to research conducted at Harvard University, the main thing for students in blended learning is not the online elements of the course, but the way the material is delivered by the teacher, so this the human factor is also of great importance in educational technology.

The main idea of blended learning is not that part of the learning process takes place online, but that the learner has the opportunity to independently control the time, place and pace of learning. The content is that the learner decides where, how, when and at what speed to study. Address and space are included in the concept of blended learning. When the learning process is fully implemented through information communication technologies, but this very component (the learner's choice of time, place, pace, and path) is removed, we can see the beautiful use of technology as a result, but upon exiting the educational system, we witness the formation of a person who is not ready to make his own choices and decisions.

We will consider their pedagogical analysis in detail.

1. Face-to-Face Driver. The instructor provides the bulk of the in-person learning plan, with online learning added as a supplement when needed. This model often includes computer lab work.

2. Online Driver Model ("Online management model"). This model mainly involves online education. Remote communication with the teacher is carried out. But on demand, audited classes and meetings with the teacher can be added.

3. Flex Model ("Flexible model"). An online platform is often used, with the tutor deploying students as needed, occasionally working with small groups or individual tutors.

4. Online Lab ("Online laboratory"). An online platform is used to transmit the entire course in classrooms. This educational process takes place under the supervision of the teacher. Such a program can be combined with a traditional program within the curriculum.

5. Self-Blend Model. The learner decides which Brick and Mortar courses to supplement with online training.

6. Rotation Model ("Rotational model"). The schedule of traditional full-time education in the auditorium and independent online education in private mode is rotated. For example, through

the Internet, on a special site, in the blended program of the institution, according to the plan of links prepared by the teacher.

There are several types of "rotational model". One of them is a flipped classroom or flipped learning, which is characterized by a radical "reversed learning" of the educational process and a departure from the traditional form of education. In his researches. Some scientists of the CIS named this type of teaching as "reversive teaching" in their research work. They believe that the term "reversed learning" is the most appropriate, because this phrase reflects the main idea - the idea of reorganizing the main components of the learning process, so that the direction of learning is changed.

In 2007, the concept of flipped learning was introduced to the scientific community by American chemistry teachers Jonathan Bergman and Aaron Sams. Their initial task was to free up the study time in favor of practical exercises instead of explaining the theoretical material by the teacher. Based on the idea of J. Bergman and A. Sams, theoretical material should be studied remotely and independently, homework should be done in class.

The analysis shows that the pedagogical technology of "Flipped Class" has been further developed with the expansion of modern computer technologies, distance learning, and Internet network opportunities, and in turn, the practical application of this technology is becoming more and more popular among teachers and students around the world. teachers started posting their audio and video lectures on local and global networks.

Conclusion: Based on the analysis of the above models, we can say that the concept of mixed education, which includes the ability to optimally combine the advantages of traditional and distance education technologies and use them, serves to increase the efficiency of the training process.

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